

Penrose Spaces

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Abstract

Roger Penrose, the greatest living 20th century scientist, proposed a radical new theory called *Twistor theory*. Working with Michael Atiyah and Ted Newman, he put forth the idea that Yang-Mills theory exchanges some of the properties of general relativity with quantum mechanics. Penrose has successfully predicted hawking points using Conformal Cyclic Cosmology.

Penrose strongly suggests [1] that models with a number of dimensions closer to 4 are best suited for describing reality. However, it is not clear if this is the "actual reality," or the "empirical reality." He viciously railed against QM's ∞ -dimensional Hilbert spaces. In particular, their flatness and linearity make them incompatible with GR. Therefore, we need *Twistor theory*.

A basic space with two real dimensions is $\mathbb{C}P^1$. Once we define the embedding $\varepsilon : \mathbb{A}^1 \hookrightarrow \mathbb{C}P^1$, we can talk about displacements of basis vectors generating the affine line as a polynomial. Obviously, if the boundary of the space is closed by a sphere, then the line will intersect the solid sphere at two antipodal points.

$$\mathbb{A}^1 \cap S_{Sol}^1 = \{*_a, *_b\} \tag{0.1}$$

Actually, since this line can take on many possible orientations (an $SO(3)$ -worth), it is better to name each orientation. When we desire to be more specific, we denote these orientation by a superscript. so, we have:

$$\xi = *_a^{L \vee R} \tag{0.2}$$

Twistor theory basically introduces a more geometrically intuitive *curvature* to the complex Hilbert space. These ideas, are due to Ted Newman and Roger Penrose, two of the pre-eminent 20th century physicists.

Penrose, in particular, does not care about generalizations of the simplest spaces to versions of themselves with higher numbers of dimensions. While they may be beautiful to him, they do not indicate any physical reality, in the actual sense. This is a scathing critique of string theory, and one that is in fact difficult to defend against.

We rewrite (0.2) as:

$$\varepsilon^P \tag{0.3}$$

where P is a *Pauli matrix*¹. There is an obvious embedding:

$$\varepsilon^P \hookrightarrow D^1(\xi) \tag{0.4}$$

*Independent

†Independent

¹any of them are fine

where D^1 is the collection of diffeomorphisms. These diffeomorphisms deform the fabric of a class of relativistic frames. Thus, if we place a measuring device M inside our manifold, and transport it around a bit, then its values will differ, corresponding to scalar curvature. This is quite literally a non-flatness of the fundamental field(s) we select for.

Penrose describes rays of light with five degrees of freedom. I am not sure how he comes to this number (perhaps he could explain it better). I believe the modern symplectic geometer would call this a “contact space.” Do recall that a contact space is a manifold

$$\mathbb{R}^{2n+1} = \text{Cont}_n \tag{0.5}$$

This is a desirable space to mathematicians (Penrose would agree) because it is a simple space with a convenient metric; the metric of the contact manifold always includes only plusses. If you’re a particle physicist, this is a nightmare. This is because the particle physicists needs to talk about *decays* and *scattering processes*, which happen *over time*.²

In order to salvage this, we need to talk about Wick rotations of Cont_1 , which are essentially deformations of the contact form. The arrangements and other properties of atoms (or strings) in the manifold are determined, up to equivalence, by these rotations.

The general formula is rather boring. It is simply the addition of two complex conjugates. This is, as you may recall, a real number, as the imaginary parts cancel out. So, all we’re left with are real measurements. However, as of now, our computing power is severely limited, and so instead we work with the rational numbers.

It turns out that a long of things are actually *more difficult* to do with the rational numbers than the real numbers. For instance, much of smooth topology, which fundamentally requires Dedekind cuts, becomes inaccessible.

Luckily, we have a saving grace: *simplicial (co)homology*. This technique involves counting triangles, as well as re-ordering the edges and vertices of the triangle to form new triangles. The most important maps are the *shift map*, and the *coshift map*. These are denoted by:

$$\mathcal{S}(\Delta) \tag{0.6}$$

and

$$\mathcal{S}^{Op}(\Delta) \tag{0.7}$$

for any triangle Δ . They represent the map $\{1, 2, 3\} \mapsto \{2, 3, 1\}$ and $\{1, 2, 3\} \mapsto \{3, 1, 2\}$. A triangle is a small simplicial complex; in fact, it is the smallest closed 2-dimensional one. This is no coincidence. The five-dimensional path of a light ray decomposes as

$$\mathbb{M}^{2+1} \oplus \mathbb{C}^1 = \mathbb{M}^2 \oplus \mathbb{C}^1 \oplus \mathbb{R}^1 = \mathbb{M} \oplus \mathbb{M} \oplus \mathbb{C} \oplus \mathbb{R} \tag{0.8}$$

and it is none other than the path of a photon through the lightcone $\mathbb{M}^{3+2}$, where $\mathbb{M}$ denotes the Minkowski-Penrose space.

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²A Feynman diagram, however, happens in an instantaneous moment of time.

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1 The Definition of a Penrose Space

Definition 1.1. A Minkowski-Penrose space is a conformal contact space.

Definition 1.2. A Penrose space is the sum of a Minkowski space and a complex vector bundle.

These are extremely simple extensions of a very easy space. However, they have profound implications for reforming modern high-energy physics. We can write the general Penrose space as:

$$\mathcal{P}^n = Cont_n \oplus \omega^n \tag{1.1}$$

Modern-day string theory is essentially:

$$\mathcal{P}^1 \oplus \mathcal{P}^1 \tag{1.2}$$

but, oftentimes, only spaces

$$\mathcal{T}_j^k = k\mathcal{P}^1 \ominus (k \pm j)\mathbb{R}$$

are considered. Let us call these³ *test spaces*. The benefits of test spaces are that they are more easily mapped to visualizable datasets using modern machine learning technology. This means that many test spaces may be compared with little tedium on the part of the human. As an example, consider the case of mapping a two-dimensional dataset onto a lightcone. This is a very insightful (and easy!) task to perform using an AI such as Google Collab, as it shows us the *twistor* data embedded into the very useful lightcone $\mathbb{L}^{2+1}$.

As per Penrose, there is a singularity at the center of the null vector space. This is because this is the asymptotic limit for both the ordinary and time-reversed equations of motion.

Once one compares several millions of variations of test space⁴-lightcone mappings, we can obtain a statical distribution of exchange particles on a Penrose space. Remarkably, due to the wave-particle duality, and the strong experimental evidence for gravitational waves, this implies a stochastic manifestation of gravity.

This is therapeutic, as it comes one step of the way towards reconciling gravity with relativity; in other words, it is a viable candidate for *quantum gravity*. The exact gravitational disturbances can be written:

$$QGrav_{p,p' \in \mathcal{P}^n, \mathcal{P}^m} = \frac{\left(\frac{1}{(2\pi)^{\otimes n}} \varepsilon^P \otimes \mathcal{P}^n \right) \oplus \left(\frac{1}{(2\pi)^{\otimes n}} \varepsilon^{P'} \otimes \mathcal{P}^m \right)}{d(p, p')} \tag{1.3}$$

This is essentially one way to mathematically derive Newton's law of gravity. Actually, we can write

$$QGrav_{p,p' \in \mathcal{P}^n, \mathcal{P}^m} = \int_{\mathcal{P}^1} \frac{\partial G_{Newton}}{\partial F} \tag{1.4}$$

³In the spirit of Grothendieck

⁴Ignoring the negative ones

where F is the action of the field.

The upshot to this theory is that it avoids explicit reference to any so-called *Higgsing mechanisms*. This means we get away with doing a lot with relatively simple topology. In addition, since we began working with spheres for our particles, we can extend them into cylinders:

$$\mathcal{C}_n = S^n \oplus L_{Ver} \cong S^{n+1} \tag{1.5}$$

where L_{Ver} is the verticle (length-wise) component of a vector bundle. For our purposes, we don't really need to work with the horizontal component.

2 P-Branes

It is actually most helpful to the string theorist to think of the Penrose space $\mathcal{P}^n$ as a AdS_3 -brane with a Gl_{u_2} field functor. This makes it into a simple fivebrane

$$\mathcal{M}^5 \tag{2.1}$$

Which, as Zanthius suggests, is a Möbius band of dimension 5.

The Wick rotations:

$$f : \mathcal{M}^5 \rightarrow \mathcal{M}^5 \oplus i\mathcal{M}^5 \tag{2.2}$$

and

$$f^{op} : \mathcal{M}^5 \oplus i\mathcal{M}^5 \rightarrow \mathcal{M}^5 \tag{2.3}$$

are used to represent the motion of a worldsheet on a lightcone.

The smallest category containing the Wick rotations (let's call it **Wick**) is a groupoid.

2.1 Orbifolds

Since we are talking about lightcones, we must remember that Penrose spaces are actually *orbifolds* rather than general *manifolds*. This is because of a very special 3-sphere at the center called **b**. Using modal logic, we define the inclusion:

$$\mathbf{b} \in \square^3 \tag{2.4}$$

where $\square$ is a *necessary* event.

To interpret this, it means that there is always a cross-section of the entire spacetime manifold containing all of the atoms, radiation, and energy of the present moment. We can verify this using even the most simple observations: the act of using any of our five senses. This sort of "God-given" ability to perceive the singularity of a lightcone⁵, I take, is proof of the necessity of orbifolds.

My philosophy is, the single necessary moment at the center of the lightcone the collection of all relative frames of reference (RFoR).

Recall that for a real manifold (with or without corners) $\mathbb{R}^4$ admits a map:

$$\mathfrak{Tw}\mathfrak{F}\mathfrak{ld}(\mathbb{R}^4) : \mathbb{R}^4 \rightarrow \mathbb{L}^{1+3} \tag{2.5}$$

which can be seen as twisting and folding a space of complex dimension 2:

$$\mathbb{R}^4 = \Re(\mathbb{C}^2) + \Im(\mathbb{C}^2) = \mathbb{R}^2 \oplus i\mathbb{R}^2 \tag{2.6}$$

⁵Or neighborhoods thereof

Definition 2.1. A good neighborhood is a neighborhood $\mathcal{U}(\alpha)$ which is:

- Contractible to a point: $\exists h : \alpha \rightarrow *$
- Homeomorphic to a ball of radius $k\varepsilon$ for an arbitrary $\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^n$
- Endowed with the contact or symplectic structure of $\mathbb{A}^n \oplus i\mathbb{A}^m \ni \alpha$

In order to justify this definition, remember that we want to talk about the most *relevant* sectors of the lightcone, which should have (to minimize our headaches) the same properties as $\mathfrak{b}$. The hidden assumption here is that when we talk about the relevant (to the present) mechanics of $\mathbb{L}^{n+m}$, we need to talk about the sphere spectrum $\mathbb{S}^{n+m}$. This should be thought of as:

$$\bigcup_{i+j} n_i \oplus m_j \quad (2.7)$$

where we have:

$$n = \bigcup_i n_i \quad (2.8)$$

and

$$m = \bigcup_j m_j \quad (2.9)$$

This is fantastic! We can now think of m and n as being the vector sum of *probability amplitudes*, which we write as vectors (1-tensors): $\vec{m}$ and $\vec{n}$, which live in a Frechét space. These are the eigenvectors of the S-matrices $M \times N$ and $N \times M$. In the massless case, these become lightlike values; the easiest such manifestation of this is the *photon*, but we can generalize to *force carriers* of any field. We need a vector-enriched topological category:

$$\mathbf{TV} \cong \mathbf{Vec}_{\mathcal{T}op} \quad (2.10)$$

in order to hold these suckers.

The preferred metric for a given quantum field is:

$$\|\mathbb{F}\| = \sqrt{k^2 + i^2} \quad (2.11)$$

$$= \sqrt{k^2 - 1} \quad (2.12)$$

This is really a dimensionless quantity, which is kind of useless for us. We need to couple to a unit $\hat{\varepsilon} \in \mathbb{F}^\times$. We can get some nice things if we define $\hat{\varepsilon} = k^2 - k$. Then we get:

$$\|\mathbb{F}\| = k + \hat{\varepsilon} - 1 \quad (2.13)$$

and when we use natural units, we set both k and $\hat{\varepsilon}$ to 1 and get:

$$\|\mathbb{F}\| \cong \mathbb{1} \quad (2.14)$$

which is the category of one-object groupoids with smooth endomorphisms.

We define a map:

$$\Omega_{\|\mathbb{F}\|} = \mathbb{F} \rightarrow \tau \in [0, 1] \subseteq \mathbb{1}_\infty \quad (2.15)$$

where

$$\mathbb{1}_\infty = C^\infty(\mathbb{1}) \quad (2.16)$$

which is a classical topos theory map known as the “*subobject classifier*.” If our space is discrete, we replace this with:

$$\Omega_{\|\mathbb{F}\|}^{Disc} = \mathbb{F} \rightarrow \{0, 1\} \subseteq \mathbb{1} \quad (2.17)$$

Technically, we are abusing notation here; by $\mathbb{1}$, we mean an *enriched* version of $\mathbb{1}$ which we can perform differentiation over. This all but mandates an ∞ -category, and in the smooth case, we are working with an (∞, ∞) -category, where the equivalences are given by objects whose distance is $< \varepsilon$ apart.

Now, this is somewhat unorthodox, but we can make this even easier for us if we let ε be a simple infinitesimal; that is, we take $\mathbb{F} = \mathbb{R}_{Hyp} = \mathbb{R} \cup \varepsilon$, where $\varepsilon < r \quad \forall r \in \mathbb{R}$. At this point, we can actually make a simple replacement by using the *Levi-Civita field*, $\mathcal{R}$. This is an extension of $\mathbb{R}_{Hyp}$ where we define quantities ε^n for every natural number (at least). Then, we come to a remarkable conclusion:

Theorem 2.1. *Every metrizable line of unit quantity can be mapped to a point.*

Which implies

Theorem 2.2 (Corollary). *Every subspace of a good neighborhood is contractible.*

which follows by definition of a *good neighborhood*.

Now, we have two items here, and they need to be described: ε and $\hat{\varepsilon}$. The first is purely a mathematical tool to make the symbols more beautiful; the second is an observable quantity, which requires a measuring device. There is some tension here between the two competing mindsets. While the mathematical theory aims to perfect our knowledge of all possible worlds, the physical purely cares about what is seen within our own universe. At this point, I must side with the mathematicians.

However, Penrose’s treatment, alongside the prescription made here, goes a long way towards uniting the two communities.

3 Force Field Quantization

Since we know charges are quantized. this means that the theoretical minimum measurable value of force must be equal to or less than the value of the lowest quantum, which is embedded in the inequality $\varepsilon \leq \liminf \hat{\varepsilon}$; this is inherited from the inequality:

$$\liminf \mathcal{R} \leq \liminf \mathbb{R}_{Hyp} \quad (3.1)$$

Because the hyperreals are uncountably infinite, it would appear that $\mathcal{R}$ suggests a better model beyond what is ever computationally possible at any given instantiation of $\mathfrak{b}$.

Definition 3.1. *A fluxion, ε_{Newton} , is equal to $\frac{\varepsilon^n}{n \rightarrow \infty}$, which is equal to $\limsup_{\mathcal{R} \rightarrow \infty} \varepsilon^{\mathcal{R}}$.*

The fluxion describes a minimal action of the relativistic point particle. Since we can contract all of the bits of our neighborhood to points, this is an indispensable ingredient! Essentially, no matter where we choose $\mathfrak{b}$ to be (or in otherwords, no matter which $\mathfrak{b}$ we choose), we can always

identify the immediate past and future as differing from the current point in time and identify it as $\partial^\pm(\mathbf{b}) = \mathbf{b} \pm \varepsilon_{Newton}$. This translates to a worldsheet perturbation:

$$\mathbf{b}^\pm = \mathbf{b} \pm \sin(e^{ik\theta\pi}) \mp \cos(e^{i(k-1)\theta\pi}) \quad (3.2)$$

where

$$\mathbf{b} = \square \cong \mathbb{T}^4 \quad (3.3)$$

where $\mathbb{T}$ is the interval of frequencies of $\mathbf{b}^\pm$ when written as a Fourier transform of $\mathbf{b}$. Denote the elements of $\mathbb{T}$ as $\{T_0, T_1, \dots, T_\infty\}$. Then we have

$$T_N ||\mathbb{F}|| = \partial F \quad (3.4)$$

where F is the force exchanged by the particle:

$$\partial F = \partial_{in} F - \partial_{out} F \quad (3.5)$$

The energy of the particle is:

$$E = ||\mathbb{F}|| \partial F \quad (3.6)$$

where $||\mathbb{F}||$ is the distance between the interacting particles. This quantity is one-dimensional, and represents the shortest path between the two particles.

For a more complicated system, we have:

$$E_{[\mathbb{F}]} = \frac{\sum_{n=0}^N \mathbb{F}_n}{N} \quad (3.7)$$

which is always a local value of a field, called the *vibration* of a neighborhood $\mathcal{U}(\alpha)$ (we oftentimes neglect to denote the neighborhood if it is understood), and we call N the *vibration number*, and every $\mathbb{F}_n$ is called an *vibration mode* of the field. The map:

$$\hat{\psi}_n : \mathbb{F}_n \mapsto E_{[\mathbb{F}]} \quad (3.8)$$

is called the “wavefunction collapse map.” We think of $\mathbb{F}_n$ as one of N many overlapping waves; the right-hand side is ambiguously either a single particle or an exchange event. We can scale the resolution up by applying:

$$\hat{\psi}_m^n = \hat{\psi}_n \circ \hat{\psi}_m \quad (3.9)$$

for any $m < n$. If we choose n to be significantly higher than m (which we are free to denote by ∞), we obtain a form of work-locking known as the *quantum Zeno effect*. As we increase our refresh rate, so to speak, to an absurdly high value, we obtain almost no change between frames.⁶ This tells us that in order to have a “good” time-step operator, we need to choose a relatively small codimension between for $\mathbb{A}^m$ in $\mathbb{A}^n$. Inherent in this assumption is that living beings can only perceive small differences between their present and their immediate past and future.

Definition 3.2. *The work-lock map is a map: $\psi_m^{n \rightarrow \infty}$.*

⁶In the relativistic limit with the Levi-Civita as our ground field, we actually obtain no change

Essentially, when we try to access an infinite amount of information, our computer/mind “freezes,” i.e., we perceive the world in $\frac{n}{\infty}$ time, which we are free to define as $(1 \pm 1)i\varepsilon$. We can perform the Wick rotations to get rid of these, by adding the complex conjugate and obtaining 2ε , and we set:

$$2\varepsilon = \frac{2\hat{\varepsilon} - \beta}{c^2} \quad (3.10)$$

where $0 < \beta < k^2 - k$.

We call β the “excitement” of the operator $\psi_m^{n \rightarrow \infty}$. Denote the local excitement of a good neighborhood $\mathcal{U}(\alpha)$ by β^* and the global excitement by $\beta^{\mathcal{M}^{m+n}}$. By the law of thermodynamic averaging, we have:

$$\beta^{\mathcal{M}^{m+n}} \propto \beta^* \quad (3.11)$$

which we read as “the local excitement varies as the global excitement.”

A References

- [1] R. Penrose, C. Jaimungal, *Penrose and Jaimungal (ToE Podcast)*, (2024)
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